

ISic1083

I.Sicily inscription 1083

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

2018.07.17 Prag

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

area of the 'tomb of Theron' in C19

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale Archeologico Pietro Griffo, inventory C1880

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Θεοῖς Κ(αταχθονίοις) .
2. Θεανῶ ἔζησεν
3. ἔτη · ιθ · μ(ῆνας) · β' · ἡμέρ(ας) · ιβ ·
4. Σαβεῖνα μήτηρ θυ
5. γατρι παρθένω ἄμο
6. λύντῳ γλυκυτάτη

Apparatus

Text based on autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492712

EDR 136099
EDCS 39102241
PHI 140566

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0264 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)
Griffo, P. 1987. Il museo archeologico regionale di Agrigento. Rome. At 188 fig.164

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Photo J. Prag, courtesy Museo Archeologico Regionale P. Griffo, Agrigento